
**CHALLENGES FACED, FACTORS IMPACTING CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP
MANAGEMENT AND SERVICE QUALITY EXPECTATIONS - A STUDY W.R.T.
SELECTED PRIVATE SECTOR BANKS AT BENGALURU URBAN****AjatashatruSamal**

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Abstract:

Customer Relationship Management (CRM) has emerged in India as a consequence rising demand of changed behaviour of customers, their preference, changes in financial market and modern technologies. The fulfillment of needs and providing faster service can be achieved only in case if banks maintain relationship with their customers (JolenaCvijovic et al. 2017).

The main motto of CRM in any organisation is to build relations with customers (Rigby et al., 2003) and then acquire new customers, treating each customer differently, retain the existing customers and maximise their life time value (Tuzhilin, 2012). Therefore the now banks now emphasize in total customer satisfaction which indicates that customer is satisfied and delighted regarding using a particular service (Shailja Pal., 2018). Private banks in Bengaluru in order to survive have to understand the consumer expectations with regard to service delivery levels and product quality (Siva Prasad, 2013). The challenge before the private banks at Bengaluru is use of collected valid information to decide the best time to offer the most needed bank products.

Banks are facing a multiple number of challenges like fierce competition from public sector banks. Changing climate and more demand from customers. Therefore customer satisfaction is the key for all problems and challenges faced by the banks. Private commercial bank has to introduce customer friendly eco products and satisfy the needs. Customer satisfaction is key for many banks to survive in competition (Snehal Kumar H Mistry, 2013). CRM is a business strategy which increases customer value and ensures that customer stays loyal. Building up of loyal customers in banks ensures sustainability and profitability. Banks which have made inadequate investment in CRM are losing fierce competitive market (Taranham Syed et al. 2014). The CRM in banks much depends upon good relation between bank executives and customers. CRM is a consideration of human factors, maintenance factors, technological factors and strategy management practices (Jayanthi et al., 2019). Against the background that majority of private banks use CRM as a strategy for better survival with profitability an attempt is made

to study how far socio-economic factors impacts CRM, challenges faced, factors impacting long term relation between private banks and customers and service quality expectation by the respondents is studied.

The present study considers both primary and secondary data and convenient sampling techniques is employed. The study found about favourable presence of socio-economic factors and analysed the factors impacting the long term relationship between banker and consumer like mobile banking, customer satisfaction and ability of bank to meet customers need etc., Further the study also found and ranked the service quality expectation like banks operate in convenient time, banks possess modern equipments and satisfactory physical facilities.

Keywords : *Relationship, loyalty, technology, skill, error free customer satisfaction, quick, contact, ability, mobile banking, favourable, challenges.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Indian banking industry is undergoing a sea of changes. The opening up of the economy in the 1990s due to liberalisation and the government decision to privatize banks amalgamation of banks with an intention of earning more profits and to reduce operational cost. Banks could improve the profitability by adopting strategies like market segmentation, innovation and better relationship. Big corporate customers have shifted their loyalty and they are rising financial needs directly from the market. Commercial banks have become more retailer - centric by offering a wide range of services (Siva Prasad, 2017). Private banks as per the previous studies reveals that they are restoring aggressive sales promotion and door-to-door campaign to attract new customers. The public sector banks after nationalisation are over burdened with social responsibilities.

The customer centric process one of the strong driver of CRM assists in creating superior value for the company and acquiring new customers (Guenzi and Troilo, 2007). The customer centric process contains the collection of customer data, finding the host of customer, evaluation and analysis of data, using customer knowledge in specific activities (Parvatiyar&Sheth, 2001; Sing, Swift, 2001).The data processing capacity being a catalyst fueled the CRM movement which is essential to an environment that permits business to take a 360 degree view of its customers (Kothandraman et al., 2000; Xu et al., 2002). Companies that successfully implement CRM will reap the rewards in customer loyalty and long term profitability (Chem&Poovaiah, 2003). CRM strategy is considered as the focused business strategy which helps to build collaborative, cooperative and profitable long term relationship with customer (Chalmeta, 2006). Customers who are satisfied with service quality are less likely to shift to other banks and hence enhances retention and loyalty (Angelis et al., 2005). Customers retention enhances profits (Becker et al.,

2009). Therefore if the organisations want to retain their customers they must develop and efficiently execute a comprehensive set of relationship.

II. RESEARCH MEHODOLOGY

Need of the Study

In the globalised environment banks are struggling heavily to satisfy the needs of consumers. The banks are forced now a days to understand the needs of the customers through proper evaluation. Due to changes in socio economic characteristics people demand more and more services from banks. In order to be global the banks should implement CRM strategy and to introduce different products and services. CRM is a strategy which assist the bankers to understand the needs of customers. In order to be successful and sustainable banks should introduce more competitive products in order to retain the loyal and trusted customers. The previous studies reveal that retention is better than searching the new customers. Satisfied customers are the assets the bank. Customer who are satisfied are less likely to switch over to the rival banks and they are retained. Consumer behaviour is fast changing due to changes in socio economic characteristics. In accordance to the changing behaviour of the customer the banks should leverage their services.

Review of Literature

Dyche (2010) defined CRM is an infrastructure that allows an increase in customer value and the correct means by which to motivate valuable customers to remain loyal.

Hinson (2006) stated that a highly satisfied customer is more likely to become loyal of banking service provider and spread positive word of mouth about the service provider.

Mishra et al., (2015) in their study about impact on the outcomes of relational efforts they have expressed that it cost less to retain a customer than acquire a new customer and hence they insisted on importance of enhancing customer life value and generate customer loyalty.

Kaabachi, et al., (2017) in the context of internet banking, they have stated that trust is often stated to be the most important factor for greater adoption of online banking services and further they have stated that it develops on the basis of consumer familiarity with internet banking, perceived structured assurance, perceived website quality.

Arcand et al. (2017) found out that mobile banking service quality dimensions have an impact on trust and satisfaction. Further they have stated that trust is more associated with utilisation factors like security privacy and practicity and also stated that satisfaction is associated with factors like enjoyment and sociality.

Adapa, S. et al., (2019) in their comparative study of Indian banking sector with other countries banking sector activities and CRM indicated that developed countries bank activity have the impact on good relation with the customers.

TeshitaUke Chikako et al., (2021) stated that the purpose of customer retention is to keep a high portion of vulnerable customers through reducing customer dissatisfaction and increasing satisfaction. Further they have reported that CRM is important as it influence in customer relation or retention from customers view.

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To study socio-economic characteristics of respondents.
- 2) To analyse the challenges faced by private sector, banks in successful implementation of CRM.
- 3) To study the factors impacting long term relationship between banks and customers.
- 4) To study the service quality expectation of respondents.

Hypotheses

- 1) The socio-economic characteristics of respondents are not impacting on CRM in private sector banks.
- 2) There are no challenges faced by private sector banks in the implementation of CRM.
- 3) There are no factors impacting on long term relationship between banks and customers.
- 4) Customers in private sectors banks at Bengaluru are not expecting from service quality.

Research questions

- 1) What are the reasons for socio-economic factors not impacting on CRM.
- 2) What are the challenges faced by private sector banks at the time of implementation of CRM in banks.
- 3) Which factors impact long term relation between private banks and consumers at Bengaluru.
- 4) What are the service quality expectation of respondents at Bengaluru.

Limitations

- 1) The study is confined only to Bengaluru.
- 2) Any nature of generalisation requires further detailed study.
- 3) The post Covid-19 second wave effect was felt and the norms of government is followed. The respondents were convinced properly by convincing about the objective of the study and mutual follow of norms.

Research Methodology : Research methodology is a collective term for the structured process of conducting research (Sam Gounder, 2012). Research methodology answers all questions like, why a research study has to be undertaken, how the research problem has been desired and in what way the hypotheses has been defined. Research methodology is used to promise a clear cut idea about the researchers proposed work. The research methodology followed in the present study is survey technique. The methodology followed in the present study is survey technique. The methodology followed is all about collecting data pertaining to socio-economic characteristics of respondents, challenges faced in successful implementation of CRM, factors impacting long term relationship between banks and customer and service quality expectation of respondents.

Sampling Frame : The sampling frame includes the target population and type of private banks covered for the purpose of data collection. Salaried employees, self employed, business people, professionals and housewives were approached for the purpose of data collection. The three private banks covered by the study are HDFC, Kotak Mahindra and Axis and Yes Bank and from each bank 50 respondents were approached.

Sample and Sampling Technique : A sample of 200 were considered for the study. The sample was decided as 200 because of norms in force after Covid-19 second wave, where in physical distance, wearing of mask, sanitisation of hands before the entry into bank etc., are mandatory. Convenient sampling technique is followed in the present research work as it is convenient to approach the respondents.

Data Collection Instrument: The present study is based in both primary and secondary data. Primary data is collected by means of administering a structured questionnaire as schedule. The questionnaire was administered as schedule due to avoid of non-response, delay and incompleteness. All questions covered in questionnaire was closed ended. Secondary data compiled from journals, internet and books. The study area is a only confined to Bengaluru Urban and different bank account holders were covered in the study. The questionnaire was divided into two divisions. The first one for socio-economic variable analysis presentation and second one for the presentation and analysis of stated objectives.

Method of Data Analysis : The study adopted χ^2 , contingency co-efficient, Kendall’s co-efficient of concordance, weighted average and Garrett Ranking Technique. χ^2 studies about good fit of data and significant variation in the data, weighted average as employed to know the relative importance of the factors and Garrette ranking technique is performed only to rank the factor as per the strength of mean score and Kendall’s co-efficient of concordance was performed to know the relationship between the attributes.

III.DATAANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

TABLE I Demographic variables of respondents-A

Research question No. 1 : What are the reasons for socio-economic characteristics not impacting CRM in private banks?

Table - 1 : Socio-economic characteristics of respondents and satisfactory with digitalization.

Characteristics	χ^2	TV@0.05	df	result of χ^2	“c”	Result of ‘C’
Gender	64.98	3.841	1	Significant	0.49	High Degree
Marital Status	112.5	3.841	1	Significant	0.60	High Degree
Age in years	69.00	9.488	4	Significant	0.50	High Degree
Qualification	48.28	11.070	5	Significant	0.44	High Degree
Occupation	56.38	11.070	5	Significant	0.47	High Degree
Income (INR /month)	79.07	17.070	5	Significant	0.53	High Degree
Effectiveness of CRM	113.00	7.855	3	Significant	0.60	High Degree
CRM role in rating customers retention	76.72	7.855	3	Significant	0.52	High Degree

Source : Field Survey

Note : χ^2 = chi-square

$$‘c’ = \sqrt{(\chi^2 / \chi^2 + N)}$$

Where ‘c’ = contingency coefficient

N = Number of observations

When the value ‘c’ is equal or near 1, it means there is high degree of association between attributes. Contingency co-efficient will always to be less than 1.

Hypotheses No. 1 : H0 : There exist no significant variation in the data.

H1 : There exist significant variation in the socio-economic factors impacting the CRM.

Table - 1 depicts data relating to socio-economic characteristics of respondents. There are 143 males (71.5%) and the remaining 57 (28.5%) were females. 175 respondents (87.5%) are married and the remaining 25 (12.5%) are remained single. 81 respondents (40.5%) are belonging to the

age group of 40-60 years followed by 49 to the 30-40 years group, 30 to the group of 60 years above, 27 belonging to 20-30 years and 13 to the group of less than 20 years. The data on qualification reveals that 61 are post graduates, 49 degree holders, 22 each professional and 10th standard and 15 ITI certificate holders. Further the table reveals that 56 are employed in private sector, 38 in government service, 21 self employed and 10 were housewives. As far as effectiveness of CRM is concerned, 90 are satisfied, 85 expressed good, 15 very good and 10 said excellent. Furthermore, the respondents were also asked to rate CRM role in customers retention. 47 said satisfactory, 39 said good, 9 very good and 5 excellent. The study reveals that all socio-economic characteristics showing significant variation and contingency co-efficient revealing high degree relationship between the two attributes.

Research Question No. 2 : What are the challenges faced by private sector banks at the time of implementation of CRM?

Table - 2 : Challenges faced by private sector banks in successful implementation of CRM.

Challenges faced	SA	A	SWA	RT	RT ²
Difficulties in the evaluation of customers	21	14	6	41	1681
The challenge of providing multi-channel advertising	13	8	3	24	576
The cost of meeting strict govt. regulations and customer security and privacy requirements	6	4	3	13	169
Heavy loads of disconnected legal system and different database that store customer money related information	7	4	2	13	169
The pressure of margins & growth	8	5	3	16	256
The cost of retaining customer and developing customer loyalty	11	6	-	17	289
The challenge of meeting the needs of customers due to technology development	19	16	6	41	1681
Challenge of competing with new generation private banks & public sector banks	16	11	8	35	1225
Total	101	68	31	200	6046

Source : Field Survey

Note : SA - Strongly Agree, A - Agree, SWA - Somewhat Agree, RT - Row Total

$$\begin{aligned}
 SSR &= \sum RT^2 - (\sum RT)^2 / N \\
 &= 6046 - (200)^2 / 8 \\
 &= 6046 - 5000 \\
 &= 1046
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 W &= 12 \times SSR / K^2 N (N^2 - 1) \\
 &= 12 \times 1046 / 9 \times 8 (64-1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$= 12552 / 4536 = 2.78$$

Test the significance of W by using the chi-square statistic.

$$\begin{aligned}x^2 &= k (n-1) w \\ &= 3 (8-1) 2.78 \\ &= 3 \times 7 \times 2.78 = 58.38\end{aligned}$$

Decision : At 7 d.f. with 0.05 level of significance the TV = 14.067. The calculated value being 58.38 higher than the critical table value and hence 'w' fails to accept H₀ and accepts H₁. Therefore it is concludes here that there exist significant relationship between the factors & challenges faced by the banks.

H₁ : There exist variation in the challenges faced by private sector banks.

Table - 2 reveals data about challenges faced by private commercial banks at the time of implementation. 101 respondents (50.5%) expressed strongly agree followed by 68 (34%) agree and 31 (15.5%) somewhat agree. Out of the 101 respondents who said strongly agree 21 spoke about difficulties in the evaluation of customers, 19 stated about the challenges of meeting the needs of customers due to technology development, 16 pointed at competing with generation and public sector banks, 13 pointed at the challenge of providing multi channel advertisement. Out of 68 who said agree, 16 said about the challenge of meeting the needs of customers, 14 spoke about the difficulties in the evaluation of customers, 11 opined about competing with new generation, banks and public sector banks and 8 regretted about the challenge of providing multichannel advertisement. As far as 31 respondents who stated somewhat agree. 8 spoke about the challenge of competing with new generation banks and public sector banks, 6 each spoke about difficulties in the evaluation of customers and the challenge of meeting the needs of customers. 'w' fails to accept H₀ and accepts H₁ and hence it is concluded that there exist significant relationship between the factors of challenge & CRM.

Research question No. 3 : Which factors affect the long term relationship between the banker and customers?

Table - 3 : Factors impacting long term relationship between private banks and customers - weighted average

Factors	Weight Likert Scale	5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SDA	Total	WA
Trust in bank & its activities	f	89	51	25	22	3	200	
	fx	445	204	75	44	3	771	51.4
Existing loyalty and satisfaction	f	131	44	10	8	7	200	
	fx	655	176	30	16	7	884	58.93
Efficient communication systems	f	116	66	4	6	8	200	
	fx	580	264	12	12	8	876	58.40
Customers knowledge of bank products and services	f	120	51	15	8	6	200	
	fx	600	204	45	16	6	871	58.06
Ability of bank to meet customers needs	f	127	54	8	6	5	200	
	fx	635	216	24	12	5	892	59.47
Customer satisfaction	f	140	52	3	3	2	200	
	fx	700	208	9	6	2	925	61.67
Efficiency of providing service	f	110	61	10	12	7	40	
	fx	550	244	30	34	7	855	57.00
Responses to need	f	108	49	10	12	7	200	
	fx	540	196	54	24	13	827	55.13
Quick solving problems	f	113	59	12	9	7	200	
	fx	565	236	36	18	7	862	57.46
Fast Service	f	102	6	16	11	8	200	
	fx	510	252	48	22	8	840	56.00
Effort to reduce queuing line	f	105	70	11	8	6	200	
	fx	525	280	33	16	6	860	57.33
Attitude towards online service	f	90	75	18	9	8	200	
	fx	450	300	54	18	8	830	55.33
Mobile banking	f	144	38	8	6	4	200	
	fx	720	152	24	12	4	912	60.80
Customers opinion about new services in the future	f	84	78	18	11	9	200	
	fx	420	312	54	22	9	817	54.47
Personal contact	f	125	44	13	11	7	200	
	fx	625	176	39	22	7	869	57.93
Additional service	f	93	74	11	13	9	200	
	fx	465	296	33	26	9	829	55.27

Source : Faced Survey

Likertscale : SA - Strongly Agree, A - Agree, N - Nutral, DA - Disagree, SDA - Strongly Disagree

Weights : 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 = 15

Weighted average = Total / sum of weights

Hypotheses : H₀ : There are no factors impacting on long term relationship between banks and customers.

H₁ :There exist significant variation in the factors effecting long term relationship between customers and banker.

Table - 3 depicts data on the long term relationship impacting factors. These factors vary from trust in the bank and its activities to the additional service. To measure the long term impacting factors weighted averaged concept was employed. The opinions of respondents presented in the form of Liker scale with 5 point scale anchor points. The weights were depending the number of scale points. The opinions expressed (f) is multiplied with concerned weights (fx). The total is divided by the sum of weights ie., (5+4+3+2+1) = 15 to get the weighted average. The relative importance is gauged by the strength of weighted average. Accordingly the first relative weighted average is customers satisfaction followed by the second mobile banking and third one is about the banks ability to meet customer needs. The final relative importance was given to trust on the bank and its activities.

Research question No. 4 : What are the service quality expectation of respondents at Bengaluru?

Table - 4 : Service quality expectation by respondents in private commercial banks - Garrett Ranking Technique

Ranks		Scale & Score value of ranks												Total	MeanRa	nk
Factors	Scale value(x)	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII			
(A) Reliability																
Banks keep up the promise	f	44	32	30	29	17	10	12	8	6	4	5	3	200		
	fx	365	223	361	980	176	995	252	204	763	522	401	361	35	511	259963.00
Shows sincere interest in solving problem	f	56	45	27	19	9	11	8	6	4	5	6	4	200		
	fx	464	832	851	782	1159	504	572	384	264	160	170	162	681	315	865.79
Provides error free records	f	48	52	29	27	14	8	6	5	4	3	2	2	200		
	fx	398	437	961	914	164	778	441	628	822	201	601	02	54	341	339967.00
(B) Responsiveness																
Employees provide prompt service	f	58	47	31	16	11	9	8	7	4	3	4	2	200		
	fx	481	434	312	046	976	661	646	838	430	816	010	210	8	341	344767.23
Always willing to help	f	45	42	25	26	18	12	10	5	8	4	2	3	200		
	fx	373	530	661	650	158	610	086	244	802	203	20	136	54	511	293064.65
(C) Assurance																
Well behaviour of employees instills confidence	f	45	42	25	26	18	12	10	5	8	4	3	2	200		
	fx	373	530	661	650	158	610	086	244	802	203	20	136	81	341	2940
Transactions are	f	61	45	35	20	11	8	6	4	3	3	2	2	200		

safe	fx5063328523101220616416288176120102 54	341368468.42IV
Employees are skilled	f 58 43 31 20 5 8 11 8 3 4 5	4200
andcourtaciousfx	4814313920461220280416528352120136135	681325466.27VII

(D) Empathy

Employee understand	f 45 31 28 25 22 18 8 7 3 6 4	3200
specific need	fx37352263184815251232936384308120204108	511271463.57 XI
Banks operate on	f 58 60 33 22 15 6 2 3 4 2 3	2 200
convenient times	fx481443802578134284037296132160 68 81	341443772.18 I

(E) Tangibles

Bank possess modern	f 55 43 41 20 10 10 7 5 4 3 1	1200
equipments	fx4565356927061220560520336220160102 27	171400270.01II
Physical facilities and	f 56 45 37 22 12 6 5 3 4 2 3 4	20
amenities are	fx464837352442134267237224013216068 81	681390069.50III

satisfactory.

Source : Field Survey

Note : X - scale value

f - number of respondents

R - Rank

Mean score = Total Score / N

Table - 5 : Garrett Ranking Conversion Table

Sl.No.	$100(R_{ij}-0.5)/N_j$	Calculated value	Garrett Value
1.	$100(1-0.5)/12$	4.17	83
2.	$100(2-0.5)/12$	12.50	73
3.	$100(3-0.5)/12$	20.83	66
4.	$100(4-0.5)/12$	29.17	61
5.	$100(5-0.5)/12$	37.50	56
6.	$100(6-0.5)/12$	45.03	52
7.	$100(7-0.5)/12$	54.17	48
8.	$100(8-0.5)/12$	62.50	44
9.	$100(9-0.5)/12$	70.83	40
10.	$100(10-0.5)/12$	79.17	34
11.	$100(11-0.5)/12$	87.50	27
12.	$100(12-0.5)/12$	95.83	17

Source : (1) SubhashVadgale (2016). Village consumer behaviour towards perishable goods.A study with respect to Ahmednagar district of Maharashtra, Pezzottaite Journals, 5, (3) 2286-2287. (2) <https://pd4pro.com.edu>

Hypotheses: H_0 :There exist no significant variation in the service quality expectation of respondents.

H_1 : There exist significant variation in the service quality expectation of respondents.

Table - 4 highlights data the service quality expectation of respondents from private sector banks at Bengaluru. To measure the service quality expectation of respondents and to rank them Garrett Ranking Technique was performed. The scale value are derived by referring to the Garrett conversion table (see Table 5). The values are called Garrett values which are obtained are referred to Garrett conversion table. The first rank was assigned to the banks operation in convenient time depending upon the strength of mean score. Similarly the second rank was assigned to bank possess the modern equipments and the third rank was awarded to physical facilities and amenities are satisfactory. The final rank 12 was awarded to banks keep up promise.

IV. SUMMARY & DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS :

The present study was taken up with an intention of studying how far the socio-economic factors impact CRM in private sector banks at Bengaluru, challenges faced, factors impacting long term relationship and service quality expectation from the banks. The study also considered the experts and scholars to give more weightage to the research work. The present study adopted survey technique. Primary data was collected through proper administration of questionnaire. The respondents were approached at the bank locality after completion of transactions. The findings of the study were presented and analysed and discussed by using Chi-square, contingency co-efficient, weight average technique, Kendall's co-efficient of concordance and Garrett Ranking Techniques. The study reveals about the presence of favourable socio-economic characteristics of respondents impacting very much on CRM and its implementation. Further the study reveals about the challenges faced by the banks like difficulties in evaluation of customers, challenge of meeting the needs of customer and competition from generation banks and public sector banks. The study also reveals about the factors like customer satisfaction, mobile banking and ability to meet the needs of customers etc., are impacting long terms relationship between private banks and customers. To measure the impacting factors weighted average concept was performed and this quantitative technique reveals about the relative importance of factors impacting long term relationship between banker and customer. The quality expectations are measured and presented. The study uses Garrett ranking technique to rank the service quality expectation by the respondents. First rank was awarded to banks operate in a convenient time followed by second rank was awarded to banks possess modern equipments and third rank was assigned to physical facilities and amenities are satisfactory.

Based on the responses from respondents it was found the banks are facing challenges like difficulty in the evaluation of customers, factors impacting long term relationship includes customer satisfaction and mobile banking. Further it is also revealed that customers exception

which was ranked by using Garrett ranking technique reveals that private banks operate in convenient time as the first rank, second rank was awarded to bank possess modern equipments and third rank was assigned to physical facilities in the bank. Convenient sampling technique was adopted to collect the data. However, questionnaire was administered as schedule to collect the most reliable data. The secondary sources include journals internet and books.

V.CONCLUSION

In order to sustain in the severe competitive world banks has to introduce CRM strategies which help them to retain than searching the new customers. The satisfied customer will be more loyal to the banks and shows less interest to switch over to the rival banks. Banks at Bengaluru are providing more competitive products including ATM withdrawal more than public sector banks ceilings. Further, in private banks provide more service than the public banks. There are no long lines in private banks which is a common feature in the public banks. Cheque book issue takes too much time and the automatic kiosk of passbook print goes out of order regularly. The study reveals clearly there exist a favourable socio-economic factors impacting CRM at Bengaluru. The challenges faced includes the difficulty of customer evaluation and meeting the needs of the customer. Further the study highlights factors like customer satisfaction, mobile banking and the ability to meet the needs of customers. The study also rank the banks operate in convenient time, possess better equipments and physical facilities which are going to impress to mind of customers.

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